

SPECTROPHOTOMETRIC STUDY OF THE FERRIC THIOSULPHATE COMPLEX. PART II

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Simple and direct experimental evidence has been described which establishes the formula $\text{FeS}_2\text{O}_3^\pm$ for the labile coloured intermediate produced by the reaction of thiosulphate with ferric salts.

In a previous communication (this *Journal*, 1956, 33, 243) the coloured complex, produced by the reaction of thiosulphates with ferric salts, was assigned the formula FeS_2O_3^+ by the application of Job's method to its absorption in mixtures of varying compositions of Fe^{3+} and $\text{S}_2\text{O}_3^{2-}$ ions. This communication provides a direct and simple experimental evidence to establish the above formula for the coloured complex. Schmid (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1930, 148, 321) have shown that the equilibrium

is instantaneously established. So the instability constant $K_{\text{FeS}_2\text{O}_3^+}$ may be denoted by the expression

$$K_{\text{FeS}_2\text{O}_3^+} = \frac{[\text{Fe}^{3+}][\text{S}_2\text{O}_3^{2-}]}{[\text{FeS}_2\text{O}_3^+]} \quad \dots (2)$$

If the product of the concentrations of Fe^{3+} and $\text{S}_2\text{O}_3^{2-}$ ions is kept constant while the concentration of each one of them is changed, the concentration of FeS_2O_3^+ just at the time of mixing the two solutions (since the complex disappears with time) must be constant provided other factors, such as the ionic strength, H^+ ion concentration and temperature, remain unaltered. According to Beer's law

$$\log I_0/I = \epsilon \cdot c \cdot d$$

where I_0 is the intensity of the incident light, I that of the light transmitted, c is the concentration of the absorbing species in moles per litre, d is the thickness of the cell and ϵ , the extinction coefficient. The value of $\log I$ at zero-time can be determined from the extrapolation of the curve obtained by plotting $\log I$ against time. Since all other terms involved in the above expression are constant, $\log I_0/I$ is proportional to c . So, if the formula of the coloured complex is FeS_2O_3^+ , then

$$\frac{[\text{Fe}^{3+}] \times [\text{S}_2\text{O}_3^{2-}]}{\log I_0/I \text{ at zero-time}} \quad \dots \quad \dots (3)$$

must be constant. On the other hand, if the formula is $\text{Fe}(\text{S}_2\text{O}_3)_2^-$, then

$$\frac{[\text{Fe}^{3+}][\text{S}_2\text{O}_3^{2-}]^2}{\log I_0/I \text{ at zero-time}} \quad \dots \quad \dots (4)$$

must be constant.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

The details of the experimental procedure were reported in the previous part (*loc. cit.*). A solution of ferric perchlorate in perchloric acid was prepared by double decomposition of ferric sulphate in sulphuric acid with calculated quantity of barium perchlorate in perchloric acid. A solution of sodium perchlorate was used for maintaining constant ionic strength. To 5 c.c. of the solution of ferric perchlorate containing perchloric acid of a given strength, 5 c.c. of an aqueous solution of sodium thiosulphate containing the required quantity of sodium perchlorate was added to bring the ionic strength of the resulting mixture to the desired value. The working temperature was $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$.

Calculation of the Concentrations of the Fe^{3+} and $\text{S}_2\text{O}_3^{2-}$ ions

It is necessary to take into account the following two side equilibria for evaluating the concentrations of the $\text{S}_2\text{O}_3^{2-}$ ion.

The values of the instability constants $K_{\text{HS}_2\text{O}_3^-}$ and $K_{\text{NaS}_2\text{O}_3^-}$ where

$$K_{\text{HS}_2\text{O}_3^-} = \frac{[\text{H}^+][\text{S}_2\text{O}_3^{2-}]}{[\text{HS}_2\text{O}_3^-]} \quad \dots (7)$$

and

$$K_{\text{NaS}_2\text{O}_3^-} = \frac{[\text{Na}^+][\text{S}_2\text{O}_3^{2-}]}{[\text{NaS}_2\text{O}_3^-]} \quad \dots (8)$$

depend on the ionic strength. These constants at any particular ionic strength can be calculated from the semi-empirical activity function (Davies, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 2093)

$$\text{Log } K = \text{log } K_0 + F(\mu),$$

where $F(\mu) = 0.505(Z_A^2 + Z_B^2 - Z_{AB}^2) \left(\frac{\sqrt{\mu}}{1 + \sqrt{\mu}} - 0.2\mu \right)$ = function of ionic strength,

K_0 = value of the constant at zero ionic strength and Z_A , Z_B , Z_{AB} are the charges on the participating ions. The values of $K_{\text{HS}_2\text{O}_3^-}$ and $K_{\text{NaS}_2\text{O}_3^-}$ for zero ionic strength which have been used are respectively 0.019 and 0.21 (Denney and Monk, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1951, 73, 4270). From the above relation the values of the constants $K_{\text{HS}_2\text{O}_3^-}$ and $K_{\text{NaS}_2\text{O}_3^-}$ have been calculated to be 0.07 and 0.78 respectively at the ionic strength 0.25; and 0.08 and 0.59 at the ionic strength 0.45. Using these values of the instability constants at the desired ionic strengths, the concentrations of free $\text{S}_2\text{O}_3^{2-}$ ion have been evaluated after accounting for the formation of ion-pairs HS_2O_3^- and NaS_2O_3^- .

The method of approximation employed for the evaluation of free $S_2O_3^{2-}$ concentration is best explained by referring to actual calculations carried out for the mixture A in Table II for the case of ionic strength of 0.25. Equations (7) and (8) can then be written as

$$\frac{[H^+][S_2O_3^{2-}]}{[HS_2O_3^-]} = K_{HS_2O_3^-} = 0.07 \quad \dots (7)$$

$$\frac{[Na^+][S_2O_3^{2-}]}{[NaS_2O_3^-]} = K_{NaS_2O_3^-} = 0.78 \quad \dots (8)$$

The actual concentrations of various ions in the mixture in g. mole per litre are as follows: $H^+ = 0.05$; $S_2O_3^{2-} = 0.005$; $Na^+ = 0.14$ (taking into consideration of $NaClO_4$ added to maintain the ionic strength along with the concentration of the reactant $Na_2S_2O_3$).

In the mixture the two ion pairs $HS_2O_3^-$ and $NaS_2O_3^-$ are instantaneously formed. The concentration of each can be calculated taking into consideration the formation of $HS_2O_3^-$ and then accounting for $S_2O_3^{2-}$ in combination as $HS_2O_3^-$, to calculate that concentration of $S_2O_3^{2-}$ forming $NaS_2O_3^-$ or *vice versa*. It is to be seen if working out of the concentration of free $S_2O_3^{2-}$ provides the same value whether concentration of $HS_2O_3^-$ is taken up first and then $NaS_2O_3^-$ and *vice versa*.

Case I.—Let x g. moles per litre of $HS_2O_3^-$ be formed, then equation (7) reduces to

$$\frac{(0.05 - x)(0.005 - x)}{x} = 0.07.$$

Simplifying and neglecting x^2 , we get $x = 0.002$. So the concentration of free $S_2O_3^{2-}$ is equal to $(0.005 - 0.002)$ or 0.003 g. moles per litre. If the formation of $NaS_2O_3^-$ is to be neglected, the value for the concentration of the $S_2O_3^{2-}$ ion becomes 0.003 g. moles per litre and not 0.0025 as taken by the authors. With the increase of Na^+ ions (as $NaClO_4$ is used for increasing ionic strength) in spite of the instability constant $K_{NaS_2O_3^-}$ being large, the concentration of $NaS_2O_3^-$ at high ionic strength would be comparable to that of $HS_2O_3^-$.

Next the formation of $NaS_2O_3^-$ is taken into account. Let y g. mole of $NaS_2O_3^-$ be formed, and in this formation the free $S_2O_3^{2-}$ has to be considered only. So equation (8) reduces to

$$\frac{(0.14 - y)(0.003 - y)}{y} = 0.78 \text{ or } y = 0.0005.$$

Thus, altogether the sum of the concentrations of $HS_2O_3^-$ and $NaS_2O_3^-$ comes to 0.0025 and that of free $S_2O_3^{2-}$ is 0.0025 .

Case II.—Let the formation of $NaS_2O_3^-$ be considered first, y denoting the concentration of $NaS_2O_3^-$ and x that of $HS_2O_3^-$ as before. Then equation (8) reduces to

$$\frac{(0.14 - y)(0.005 - y)}{y} = 0.78 \text{ or } y = 0.0007.$$

Now free $S_2O_3^{2-}$ becomes $(0.005 - 0.0007)$ or 0.0043 g. moles per litre. So equation (7) reduces to

$$\frac{(0.05 - x)(0.0043 - x)}{x} = 0.07 \text{ or } x = 0.0017.$$

Thus, the concentration of $S_2O_3^{2-}$ in combination becomes (0.0007 + 0.0017) or 0.0024, and the concentration of free $S_2O_3^{2-}$ becomes 0.0026.

Working out in the similar manner, it has been seen that this method of approximation affords concordant values, and so the authors have used it. In the subsequent papers the same method of approximation has been used.

In order to calculate the concentration of free Fe^{3+} ions, the equilibrium

is to be considered. The value of the instability constant $K_{FeOH^{2+}}$, where

$$K_{FeOH^{2+}} = \frac{[FeOH^{2+}][H^+]}{[Fe^{3+}]} \quad \dots (10)$$

varies with both the ionic strength and temperature. According to Bray and Hershey (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 56, 1889) its values at the two ionic strengths 0.25 and 0.45 and at 25° have been taken to be 19.9×10^{-4} and 18.6×10^{-4} respectively. Thus, knowing the value of $K_{FeOH^{2+}}$ and the concentrations of H^+ and Fe^{3+} initially present, the concentration of $FeOH^{2+}$ can be calculated. This value, when subtracted from the initial concentration of the Fe^{3+} ion, provides the concentration of the free Fe^{3+} ion. In the above calculation the equilibrium (Milburn and Vosburgh, *ibid.*, 1955, 77, 1352),

has not been taken into account since it would not affect substantially the concentration of the Fe^{3+} ion.

In Tables I and II are recorded the values of the percentage of transmission (*I*) at ten second intervals for each mixture at two different wave-lengths (500 m μ and 600 m μ) and for two ionic strengths (0.25 and 0.45). The logarithms of these values are also shown in the above tables. The composition of each mixture indicates the concentrations (not their effective concentrations) of the various substances present in one litre of the mixture when the two solutions are mixed in equal volumes (5 c.c. each). The two mixtures are denoted by A and B as shown in the tables.

TABLE I

Time.	Ionic strength = 0.25.				Temp. = 25°.			
	Fe ³⁺ = 0.01M, S ₂ O ₃ ²⁻ = 0.005M, H ⁺ = 0.05 N.				Fe ³⁺ = 0.005 M, S ₂ O ₃ ²⁻ = 0.01 M, H ⁺ = 0.05 N.			
	Mixture (A).		Mixture (B).		Mixture (A).		Mixture (B).	
	% Transmission (<i>I</i>).		Log (<i>I</i>).		% Transmission (<i>I</i>).		Log (<i>I</i>).	
	500 m μ .	600 m μ .	500 m μ .	600 m μ .	500 m μ .	600 m μ .	500 m μ .	600 m μ .
10 secs.	22.00	24.50	1.3424	1.3892	22.75	24.50	1.3570	1.3892
20	28.00	30.00	1.4472	1.4771	29.25	31.00	1.4661	1.4924
30	38.75	40.75	1.5883	1.6101	39.75	41.00	1.5993	1.6128
40	53.50	55.50	1.7284	1.7443	51.00	51.75	1.7076	1.7139
50	68.50	69.75	1.8357	1.8435	61.00	61.50	1.7853	1.7889
60	80.50	81.50	1.9058	1.9112	69.00	69.00	1.8388	1.8388
70	88.75	89.50	1.9481	1.9518	75.00	75.25	1.8751	1.8765
80	93.00	93.75	1.9685	1.9719	80.00	79.50	1.9031	1.9024
90	95.25	96.00	1.9788	1.9823	83.00	83.00	1.9191	1.9191
100	96.25	97.00	1.9834	1.9868	85.50	85.00	1.9220	1.9294

SPECTROPHOTOMETRIC STUDY OF FERRIC THIOSULPHATE COMPLEX 463

TABLE II

Ionic strength = 0.45. Temp. = 25°.

Time.	Mixture (A).				Mixture (B).			
	% Transmission (<i>I</i>).		Log (<i>I</i>).		% Transmission (<i>I</i>).		Log (<i>I</i>).	
	500 m μ .	600 m μ .	500 m μ .	600 m μ .	500 m μ .	600 m μ .	500 m μ .	600 m μ .
10 secs.	33.00	34.75	1.5185	1.5409	33.00	35.00	1.5185	1.5441
20	36.75	39.00	1.5653	1.5911	38.50	40.75	1.5835	1.6101
30	43.25	46.50	1.6360	1.6675	45.50	48.00	1.6580	1.6812
40	52.25	56.75	1.7181	1.7540	53.00	55.50	1.7243	1.7443
50	62.25	67.50	1.7941	1.8293	60.50	63.00	1.7818	1.7993
60	71.75	77.75	1.8558	1.8907	67.25	69.00	1.8277	1.8388
70	80.00	85.50	1.9031	1.9320	74.25	74.75	1.8588	1.8736
80	86.00	90.50	1.9345	1.9566	76.75	78.75	1.8851	1.8963
90	90.00	93.50	1.9542	1.9708	80.00	82.00	1.9031	1.9138
100	92.75	95.50	1.9673	1.9800	82.50	84.25	1.9165	1.9256

The plot of log *I* against time furnishes a S-shaped curve. By extrapolating these curves to zero-time; the values of log *I* at zero time have been obtained. These values as well as those of log *I*₀/*I* at zero-time have been shown in Table III, along with the calculated values of the concentrations of the S₂O₃²⁻ and Fe³⁺ ions.

TABLE III

Mixtures	Log <i>I</i> at zero-time.		Log <i>I</i> ₀ / <i>I</i> at zero-time.		Calc. values (g. moles per litre).		$\frac{[\text{Fe}^{3+}][\text{S}_2\text{O}_3^{2-}]}{\log I_0/I} \times 10^8$ at zero-time.		$\frac{[\text{Fe}^{3+}][\text{S}_2\text{O}_3^{2-}]^2}{\log I_0/I} \times 10^9$ at zero-time.	
	500 m μ .	600 m μ .	500 m μ .	600 m μ .	Fe ³⁺ × 10 ³ .	S ₂ O ₃ ²⁻ × 10 ³ .	500 m μ .	600 m μ .	500 m μ .	600 m μ .
Ionic strength = 0.45.										
(A)	1.30	1.36	0.70	0.64	9.60	2.50	34.28	37.19	85.71	93.72
(B)	1.30	1.35	0.70	0.65	4.80	5.10	34.97	57.66	178.36	192.07
Ionic strength = 0.45.										
(A)	1.50	1.52	0.50	0.48	9.60	2.20	42.24	44.00	90.95	94.70
(B)	1.49	1.50	0.51	0.50	4.80	4.50	42.35	43.50	190.59	194.40

From Table III it is clearly evident that the value of the expression

$$\frac{[\text{Fe}^{3+}][\text{S}_2\text{O}_3^{2-}]}{\log (I_0/I) \text{ at zero-time}}$$

for a particular wave-length and ionic strength is constant, while it is not so for the expression

$$\frac{[\text{Fe}^{3+}] [\text{S}_2\text{O}_3^{2-}]^2}{(\log I_0/I) \text{ at zero-time}}$$

This conclusively establishes that the formula of the labile coloured complex is FeS_2O_3^+

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